

Marketing Mix Practices in the Development of Small and Medium Enterprises in the Bolgatanga Municipality, Ghana

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Abstract.

This paper attempts to investigate whether the practice of marketing mix aids in the development of SMEs in the Bolgatanga Municipality.

Method. The study employed a qualitative, exploratory approach with the aid of questionnaires to gather data from 119 owners of SMEs.

Results. Owners of SMEs in Bolgatanga do not see the marketing mix as strategies for building long term customer relationships but as cost to them. They therefore would prefer other personal means of showcasing, communicating and networking with their customers.

Conclusion. Although some owners of SMEs embarked on some form of marketing, they had a backward and primitive mindset of marketing mix. They viewed the marketing mix to be all about promotional sales and advertisement. That is they considered the marketing mix as a mere tactics in support of selling or advertising, rather than as a strategic planning tool needed for the development of the enterprise.

Keywords: Marketing Mix, SMEs, development, Ghana

1.0 Background to the study

The term marketing is defined as the integration of marketing programs that are used to attract and keep long-term relationship with customers (Crane, 2010). The marketing mix is a model of creating and implementing marketing strategies which stresses the blending of various factors in such a way that both organizational and consumer objectives are attained. The elements are the marketing tactics, also known as the 'four Ps', the marketing mix elements are price, place, product, and promotion.

The marketing of products and services and the ways in which communication takes place with producers and consumers in both developing and developed nations has however changed tremendously over the years. Technological revolutions and innovations such as the Internet and mobile phones now affect many millions of people, yet were almost unheard of twenty years ago. Control over information or power over information has apparently shifted from the hands of manufacturers to the hands or minds of consumers. Consequently, marketers have had to change the ways they conduct their marketing communication activities toward a more holistic customer-oriented and potentially customer-controlled process. Often this process is termed 'Marketing Mix' ('MM' in its abbreviated and perhaps more recognisable form). Marketing mix (MM) is a product of the late twentieth century. Its genesis can be traced directly to early academic work at the Medill School of Journalism, North-western University, led by Professor Don Schultz in the early 1990s (Mc Cartan-Quinn and Carson, 2003).

Media fragmentation and expansion and massive accelerated technological developments, together with budgetary constraints has some years brought about significant changes in marketing practices in companies around the world. Yet, most research to date has focussed either upon large firms (i.e. national, international, multinational and global) or the agencies (advertising and public relations agencies) that service their communications needs. Thus, a gap in the literature has been that very few studies have been conducted in relation to the conception and meaning of marketing mix from the context of small and medium sized enterprises (SMEs), and this despite the fact that the initial literature on marketing mix intimated that it was likely to be of greater relevance to smaller businesses, given their proximity to customers and their greater flexibility in relation to marketing communications in order to produce rapid returns on investment. This avenue of potential research remains almost untapped, and this proposed study is one step towards remedying the situation.

In a global sense, SMEs often form the backbone of national economies and moreover, SMEs have increased in importance recently (Mc Cartan-Quinn and Carson, 2003, Burns, 2010). SMEs and the development of SME sectors in national economies is an important element of political and public policy life. Thus, the ways these companies tackle their marketing and marketing communications activities justify a detailed investigation. Hence, the major purpose of this study is to explore if SMEs are using MM and if so, are there barriers to the adoption and applicability of MM?

There is also a growing recognition of the important role, Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs) play in economic development. They are often described as efficient and prolific job creators, the seeds of big businesses and the fuel of national economic engines. Even in the developed industrial economies, SMEs Sector is the largest employer of workers. Interest in the role of SMEs in the development process continues to be in the forefront of policy debates in most countries. Governments at all levels have undertaken initiatives to promote the growth of SMEs (Carsamer, 2009, Tyler and Stanley, 1999).

Small and Medium Enterprises in Ghana are thus said to be a characteristic feature of the production landscape and have been noted to provide about 85% of manufacturing employment of Ghana (Aryeetey, (2001)). SMEs are also believed to contribute about 70% to Ghana's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and account for about 92% of businesses in Ghana. SMEs therefore having a crucial role to play in stimulating growth, generating employment and contributing to poverty alleviation, given their economic weight in African countries. SMEs development can encourage the process of both inter and intra-regional decentralization; and, reckon force in catching up with economic superpowers of larger economies in the developed world. More generally, the development of SMEs is seen as accelerating the achievement of wider socioeconomic objectives, including poverty alleviation (Cook and Nixon, 2000).

It has however been worrisome that despite the incentives, policies, programmes and support aimed at revamping the SMEs, they have performed rather below expectation in Ghana. Different people, organisations, and operators have advanced various reasons as to why SMEs have not been able to live up to their expectations. While an average operator would always hinge his failure on lack of access to finance, some others think otherwise arguing that inappropriate management skills, huge some of foreign substitute goods, lack of entrepreneurial skills and know how, poor infrastructure etc. are largely responsible.

Some others have argued that the bane of SMEs in Ghana is the lack of long-term loans since most loans in the Ghana market are short-term while what SMEs require to grow and become really successful is long-term patient capital. The key ones include inadequate infrastructural facilities (road water electricity etc), insecurity of lives and property, inconsistent monetary, fiscal and industrial policies, limited access to markets, multiple taxation and levies, lack of modern technology for processing and preserving products, policy reversals, capacity limitations, data inadequacies, harsh operating environment, fragile ownership base, fragile capital base. While some of the challenges that SMEs face are induced by the operating environment (government policies, globalization effects, financial institutions, local government policies, attitude to work etc), other challenges are driven by the inherent characteristics of the SMEs themselves and it is with this issue why the researcher wish to look at marketing mix in the development of SMEs in Ghana

The major objective of this paper is to assess the best marketing mix practices adopted by small and medium scale enterprises in the Bolgatanga municipality in Ghana towards their development. Practically, the study intends to investigate in to the conformity of the SMEs with the traditional marketing mix practices or not. Accordingly, the following research questions are posited to elicit responses to resolve the challenge of this paper.

1. How does SMEs in the Bolgatanga Municipality conceive marketing mix?
2. Are there any other entrepreneurial marketing practices other than the traditional approach to the marketing mix practices?

2.0 Review of Related Literature

2.1 Definitions and classification of SMEs

Definitions of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) vary from country to country, depending on one or more of thresholds laid down in respect of investment, employment, turnover etc. The issue of what

constitutes a small or micro enterprise is a major concern in the literature. Different writers have usually given different definitions to this category of business. SMEs have indeed not been spared with the definition problem that is usually associated with concepts which have many components. The definition of firms by size varies among researchers as well as writers. Others define SMEs in terms of their legal status and method of production. Some attempt to use the capital assets while others use labour and turnover level.

(Bolton and Firms, 1971) first formulated an “economic” and “statistical” definition of a small firm. Under the economic definition, a firm is said to be small if it meets the following three criteria:

- It has a relatively small share of their market place;
- It is managed by owners or part owners in a personalized way, and not through the medium of a formalized management structure;
- It is independent, in the sense of not forming part of a large enterprise.

Under the statistical definition, the Committee proposed the following criteria:

- The size of the small firm sector and its contribution to GDP, employment, exports, etc.;
- The extent to which the small firm sectors economic contribution has changed over time;
- Applying the statistical definition in a cross-country comparison of the small firms’ economic contribution.

The Bolton Committee applied different definitions of the small firm to different sectors. Whereas firms in manufacturing, construction and mining were defined in terms of number of employees (in which case, 200 or less qualified the firm to be a small firm), those in the retail, services, wholesale, etc. were defined in terms of monetary turnover (in which case the range is 50,000-200,000 British Pounds to be classified as small firm). Firms in the road transport industry are classified as small if they have 5 or fewer vehicles. There have been criticisms of the Bolton definitions. These centre mainly on the apparent inconsistencies between defining characteristics based on number of employees and those based on managerial approach.

In Japan, small-scale industry is defined according to the type of industry, paid-up capital and number of paid employees. Consequently, small and medium-scale enterprises are defined as: those in manufacturing with 100 million yen paid-up capital and 300 employees, those in wholesale trade with 30 million yen paid-up capital and 100 employees, and those in the retail and service trades with 10 million yen paid-up capital and 50 employees (Ekpenyong and Nyong, 1992).

European Union (EU) Member States, traditionally have their own definition of what constitutes an SME, for example the traditional definition in Germany had a limit of 250 employees, while, for example, in Belgium it could have been 100. But now the EU has started to standardize the concept. Its current definition categorizes companies with fewer than 10 employees as "micro", those with fewer than 50 employees as "small", and those with fewer than 250 as "medium" By contrast, in the United States, when small business is defined by the number of employees, it often refers to those with fewer than 100 employees, while medium-sized business often refers to those with fewer than 500 employees. Canada also defines a small business as one that has fewer than 100 employees (if the business is a goods-producing business) or fewer than 50 employees (if the business is a service-based business), and a medium-sized business as fewer than 500. (Carsamer, 2009)

After looking at the definitions and classifications of SMEs in the global perspective, it is important to examine definitions of SMEs given in the context of Ghana. In Ghana various definitions have however been given for Micro, Small and Medium scale enterprises but the most commonly used criterion is the number of employees of the enterprise (Abor and Quartey, 2010). In using this definition, confusion often arises in respect of the unpredictability and cut off points used by the various official sources.

According to the National Board for Small Scale Industries (NBSSI,) SMEs is defined in Ghana by applying both the “fixed asset and number of employees’ criteria”. It defines a small-scale enterprise as a firm with not more than 9 workers, and has plant and machinery (excluding land, buildings and vehicles) not exceeding 10 million Ghanaian cedis and micro with employee less than five (Dalitso and Peter, 2000).

As espoused by the Ghana Statistical Service (GSS), firms less than 10 employees as small-scale enterprises and their counterparts with more than 10 employees as medium and large-sized enterprises. Ironically, the GSS in its national accounts considered companies with up to 9 employees as SMEs (Dalitso and

Peter, 2000). The value of fixed assets in the firm has also been used as an alternative criterion for defining SMEs. The Ghana Enterprise Development Commission (GEDC), on the other hand, uses a 10 million Ghanaian cedis upper limit definition for plant and machinery. It is important to caution that the process of valuing fixed assets poses a problem. Secondly, the continuous depreciation of the local currency as against major trading currencies often makes such definitions outdated (Dalitso and Peter, 2000).

In order to investigate what SME entrepreneurs really think a marketing approach is, it is necessary to recall what a marketing approach is for academic researchers. Since its first definition, provided in 1935 by the National Association of Marketing Teachers (an American Marketing Association [AMA] predecessor), according to which marketing consisted in “the performance of business activities that direct the flow of goods and services from producers to consumers” (Keefe, 2004), the marketing concept has evolved through three main different frameworks – transactional, , and induction relationship – which can be traced in the academic literature in a paradigmatic way. A brief explanation of the three frameworks includes: 1) the transactional framework which focuses on the theoretical exchange concept, implemented through the so-called marketing mix paradigm, developed by (McCarthy, 1960) and referred to the mixture of those elements (the 4Ps:Product, Price, Promotion, and Place) useful in pursuing a certain market response, 2) relationship marketing which focuses on the concept of relationship between the organization and its external counterparts (e.g., customers in the strict sense, and also suppliers, distributors, and competitors) as well as internal ones (e.g., managers and employees) (Grönroos, (2002).) 3) The induction marketing focuses on how to manipulate the expectancies (i.e., expectations and desires) and perceptions of both final consumers and other firm counterparts, in order to induce them to subscribe a firm’s objective and to be well predisposed towards its offers (e.g., inducing final consumers to buy its products, (Sergio, 2000).

2.2: Marketing Mix

The marketing mix is a model of creating and implementing marketing strategies. It stresses the blending of various factors in such a way that both organizational and consumer objectives are attained. The elements are the marketing tactics, also known as the 'four Ps', the marketing mix elements are price, place, product, and promotion. The model was developed by Neil Borden (Borden, 1964)

When blending the mix elements, marketers must consider their target market. They must understand the wants and needs of the market customer then use these mix elements in constructing and formulating appropriate marketing strategies and plans that will satisfy these wants.

According to Lee and Kotler (2011) “Marketing Mix is the set of controllable variables that the firm can use to influence the buyer’s response.” The controllable variables in this context refers to the 4 ‘P’s product, price, place (distribution) and promotion. Each firm strives to build up such a composition of 4‘P’s, which can create highest level of consumer satisfaction and at the same time meet its organisational objectives. In addition, Moor and Maidenhead, (2009) define the marketing mix as a “term used to describe the combination of tactics used by a business to achieve its objectives by marketing its products or services effectively to a particular customer group”. It is also referred to as the ‘4 Ps’ –Product, Place, Promotion and Price, or the ‘7 Ps’ – the 4 Ps with the addition of People, Process and Physical Evidence. These 4 or 7 ‘P’s are also called elements of marketing and together they constitute the marketing mix. All these are inter-related because a decision in one area affects decisions in other areas.

From the above definition, it is realized that marketing mix is basically about identifying consumers’ needs and supplying various goods and services to satisfy those needs most effectively. So, SME owners need to: produce or manufacture the product according to consumers’ need; makes it available at a price that the consumers’ find reasonable and can afford; supply the product to the consumers at different outlets they can conveniently approach; and inform the consumers about the product and its characteristics through the media they have access to (Moor and Maidenhead, 2009)

2.2 Empirical literature

According to (Adegbuyi, 2011) SMEs pay little attention to the promotion of their products. Advertising and other methods of promotion are not adequately used. Many of them do not participate in trade fairs and exhibitions. This kind of orientation inhibits their growth and ability to compete with larger companies and the

general market at large. The lack of competence and appreciation for the marketing mixes was noted by (Tsikirayi et al., 2013), in the case of Nigeria, where they noted lack of understanding the need for, and the manner of application of the marketing concept. Most of the small business players think promotion is for large businesses, which do it because they are big, whereas the reverse is true. In addition, recent research has shown that, compared with larger firms, SMEs tend to be more reluctant to adopt a marketing approach mainly because of a lack of resources and skills. (Verhees and Meulenber, 2004).

On the other hand, Sashittal and Jassawalla (2001) found in their study that implementing marketing in small firms consists of day-to-day improvisations and adaptations in marketing strategy and activities. According to them, the nature and extent of marketing improvisations and adaptations determine the level of market orientation, growth and strategic effectiveness. They argued that marketing planning and implementation interact strongly and this shape the market behaviours of SMEs and affects the strategic outcomes.

3.0 Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This study adopted the cross sectional explorative research design. Exploratory research is used as the initial research into a hypothetical or theoretical idea. This is where a researcher has an idea or has observed something and seeks to understand more about it. An exploratory research project is an attempt to lay the groundwork that will lead to future studies, or to determine if what is being observed might be explained by a currently existing theory. Most often, exploratory research lays the initial groundwork for future research. By this method, we seek to unravel marketing mix among SMEs in the Bolgatanga Municipality.

The study made an extensive use of only primary data for the purpose of the analysis. The primary data was obtained from the field using close ended questionnaire directly from the respondent in of business enterprises in Bolgatanga Municipality. SMEs managers/owners or entrepreneurs were the main respondents.

The target population of the study was all business enterprises in Bolgatanga Municipality with at least one employee. However, the categorization of firms into small and medium will depend on the number of employees. Again, business entities that were willing and cooperating with the researcher constituted the target population. Business enterprises all over the Bolgatanga Municipality therefore were part this study's population.

3.2 Sample Method and Procedure

In attempt to examine the marketing mix practices among SMEs in the study area, this study used 125 business enterprises in the research process. 125 business enterprises were used because of resource constraint. The rationale for the adoption of this number is the fact that studying large number is challenged by a lot of constraints among some are time and finances. The choice of this sample size will also be best guided by the finding of Hamill and Gregory (1997), and Kurnia and Johnston (2003), who says sampling is very important because in many cases a small sample from a population is very economical considering the nature of the study, logistics, financial constraints and the time period for the study.

This study used employed non-probability sampling techniques since the sample frame could not be established. The study therefore used a convenient sampling technique for the data collection. Despite the lack of randomness and the other accompanying defects of this sampling technique, the study tried to minimise these weaknesses by not self-selecting respondents in order to avoid biases. Sampling in this study was therefore not systematic or random but was non-selective with the aim of obtaining the highest possible number of responses with biases.

Primary data was collected pertaining to business marketing strategies from SMEs in the study area. Furthermore, the questionnaire method was chosen as a principal technique of data collection, because it afforded the advantages of vast coverage, speed, cost, less pressure and versatility. The main characteristic of this method will be that data are offered by the respondents, with limited interference on the part of researcher (Kurnia and Johnston, 2003). In spite of the fact that they do not allow probing, prompting and clarification of questions, questionnaires was still the most appropriate research instrument for this study because they offered

greater assurance of anonymity, less opportunity for bias and errors and a stable, consistent and uniform measure of variation. Besides, they also produced quick results.

The main questionnaire was developed on the basis of the preliminary findings obtained from the pre-test that was administered in a close-ended format, to the 125 SME entrepreneurs at their firm locations. A comprehensive questionnaire was therefore developed and comprised four major parts. The first section included seven questions related to owner-manager characteristics: age, sex, marital status, educational qualifications, and experience. The second section included questions related to the firm/business characteristics, including industry, age, source of financial resources and years in operation. These data were utilised to identify a more meaningful profile for the sample. In the third section, 7 questions on the perception of the marketing concept were asked to participants in order to investigate: (1) the subjective meanings attributed by entrepreneurs to the marketing concept; (2) the main function performed by marketing in their organizations; (3) the importance of marketing for their organizations, in relation to other functions; (4) whether a marketing approach has ever been adopted; and (5) the motives of its adoption, (6) type of marketing tools adopted (7) sources of marketing mix knowledge. The last section of the questionnaire explored marketing mix practices and challenges to the adoption of marketing mix among the SMEs.

3.3 Methods of Data Analysis

The process for the data analysis included data preparation (coding, editing and checks for errors and biases), counting, (registering research items and frequency of occurrences), grouping of collected data, analysing and presentation of the results. Data collected was imputed using the Statistical Product for Service Solutions (SPSS) Version 21 software and the data was analysed using STATA statistical software version 13.1. In this study, for the purpose of achieving the main research objective descriptive statistics and non-parametric statistical techniques for data analysis were employed.

4.0 Empirical Findings

4.1 Owner-Manager Characteristics

Table 4.0: Owner-Manager characteristics of small and medium enterprises

Owner-Manager Characteristics	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
<i>Age Distribution</i>		
20–30	6	6.6
31–40	33	28.7
41–50	31	30.6
51–60	20	18.5
61–70	15	13.9
Over 70	3	2.8
Total	108	100
<i>Education</i>		
No Education	4	3.7
Primary	22	20.4
JHS/JSS	71	66.7
SSS/SHS	6	5.6
Higher Level	5	4.6
Total	108	100
<i>Sex</i>		
Male	46	42.6
Female	62	57.4
Total	108	100

Marital Status		
Not Married	52	48.1
Married	56	51.9
Total	108	100
Reasons for entering business		
Personal Interest	63	56.4%
Family Business	45	41.6%
Total	108	100

The owner-manager characteristics of SMEs and their most important features from the sample are summarized in Table 4.0. As shown in Table 4.0, over half (55%) of owner/managers of SMEs within the Bolgatanga Municipality are fifty years old or younger. Based on the information provided regarding educational qualifications of Owners-managers of SMEs, 66.7% have obtained a junior high school certificate and less than 10% had their education above this level and only 3.7% had no formal education. This indicates that level of education most managers or owners of SMEs in the Bolgatanga Municipality is low. Managers or owners of businesses were also asked to indicate whether they had prior experience before entering the business and experience meant whether they had worked, had apprenticeship, attachment or even family business. 72.2% of small businesses' owner-managers had prior experience owning a similar business. In addition to the data in Table 4.0, it can be seen that 42.6% of managers of small firms are males and 54.4% are females. This however indicate that whereas small firms are female dominant. Furthermore, 51.9% of managers of small and medium businesses are married. The most important reason for entering into small business is that the firm in question is a family business (41.6%) and 56.4% accounted for personal interest. This indicates that most firms in Ghana can be said to be family businesses or mostly get support from the family, many firms' owners enter businesses in Ghana mostly as individual trades and personal interest.

4.2 Years of operation of SMEs

Table 4.1: Distribution of small and medium enterprises by age

Years in business	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 5 years	29	26.9
5 -10 years	37	34.3
11 - 15 years	19	17.6
16 - 20 years	11	10.2
21 years and Above	12	11.1
Total	108	100.0

In terms of the SMEs characteristics in the sample, the most important features are summarized in this section. As Table 4.1 indicates, the majority of the SMEs in the Bolgatanga Municipality are relatively younger as about 68% of them are below 10 years of operation. It also shows that the participating firms were fairly experienced considering their average number of years in operation. The mature status of participating firms is very encouraging for collecting objective and reliable data.

4.3: Business Ownership structure or Legal status

Table 4.2: Ownership structure or Legal status of small and medium enterprises

Legal status	<i>F</i>	%
Family Business	15	13.9
Sole Proprietorship	78	72.2
Partnership	12	11.1
Others	3	2.8
Total	108	100.0

Interestingly, most of the SMEs in the Bolgatanga Municipality operate as sole proprietors (72.2%), while a few firms operate as family business (13.9%). Again, only 11.1% of SMEs operate on partnership (see Table 4.2). Consistent extant literature, many SMEs in the study area and in Ghana are sole proprietorship in nature.

4.4 Entrepreneurs' Conception of Marketing

When SMEs entrepreneurs were asked the question "In your opinion, what is marketing mix?" many entrepreneurs were found to consider marketing simply as tactics to develop sales and firm size (51.6% of cases), to improve consumers' knowledge of the firm and its products in the marketplace (22.1%), to satisfy niche customers (13.7%), or as a tool to search for new markets (9.5%). Only 16.8% of respondents, by defining marketing as "A function involving all firm processes and resources", showed a broader view of this construct (see Table 4.4). This finding is consistent with the evidence provided by Marcati et al., (2008) which also found that many SMEs in Italy have a narrower concept of marketing mix in the business orientation and strategic management dispensation.

Table 4.3 SMEs entrepreneurs' definition of Marketing mix

SMEs Entrepreneurs' definition of marketing mix	Frequency	Percentage
Tactics to satisfy and sustain niche/old customers	13	13.7
Tools to improve consumers' knowledge of the firm and its products in the marketplace	21	22.1
A tactics to develop sales and firm size	49	51.6
A function involving all firm processes and resources	16	16.8
Tools to search for new markets and customers	9	9.5
Total	108	100.0

4.5 Function of Marketing Mix

As for the main function performed by marketing mix in their respective enterprises, SME entrepreneurs declared that marketing mix plays different alternative roles. As in Figure 4.3, the study revealed that increasing sales (40.7% of cases) is reported to be major function of marketing mix in every business establishment according to the SMEs entrepreneurs in the Study sample. Also 22.2% of the respondents reported satisfying customers as another principal function of marketing mix. Issues of communication (14.8%), developing new products (9.3%), and analysing new markets and products (8.3%) were also cited as the functions of marketing mix by some SMEs entrepreneurs in the study area. Yet again, about 4.6% of the respondent revealed that marketing mix has marginal or no function in their business establishment.

Fig: 4.0 What function does Marketing Mix Play

4.6 Reasons for adopting Marketing Mix

As for the motives of the adoption of a marketing approach, entrepreneurs indicated the possibility of improvement sales and profit (41.8%) appeared as the most imperative motive for adoption of marketing mix. This implies many businesses adopt marketing primarily to improve their sales and profit. Improving consumers’ knowledge of the firm and its products in the marketplace (28.4%) is also cited as a motive for marketing mix adoption. Other factors considered by the respondents as motives for the adoption marketing mix included favouring the firm’s development (13.4%), and improving firms’ competitiveness (16.4%) (see Table 4.4).

Table 4.4 Motives for marketing mix adoptions among SMEs

Motives for Marketing adoption	Frequency	Percentage
The improvement of consumers’ knowledge of the firm and its products in the marketplace	19	28.4
The improvement of firm’s competitiveness	11	16.4
Firm’s development	9	13.4
To improve sales and profits	28	41.8
Total	67	100.0

4.7 Reasons for not adopting Marketing Mix

Of the 41 firms that have never adopted marketing mix, a number of reasons were subscribed to as contributing to their failure or unwillingness to adopt any marketing approach in their businesses. Among these reasons are; many entrepreneurs said they do adopt marketing because it is costly (22.0%). It was also revealed that; some businesses do not adopt marketing because their managers/owners do not have expertise in marketing (31.7%). Some entrepreneurs (more than a quarter 36.6%) also said they do not adopt marketing mix because they already have strong customer base as in Table 4.6. This implies firm that think they have strong customer base do not engage in marketing their products and/or services.

Table4.5: Reasons why SMEs do not adopt Marketing mix approaches

Reason Why SMEs do not adopt Marketing mix	Frequency	Percentage
Costly	9	22.0
we don’t have the expertise in marketing	13	31.7
we have strong customer base	15	36.6
Others	4	9.8
Total	41	100.0

4.8 Sources of Marketing Mix Knowledge

Probably the following tendency can be found in the background of the not too favourable results concerning the situation of marketing knowledge sources among SMEs entrepreneurs in the Bolgatanga Municipality. Enterprises managers/owners consider the experiences obtained in the course of business satisfactory for marketing activity. About 76.1% of the respondents cited experiences from their business as the principal source of knowledge of marketing. A genuine question however arises here: what kind of knowledge these enterprises can receive from each other if none of them have formal marketing knowledge? Altogether 4.5% of the enterprises have a colleague with in most cases medium level marketing qualification. Some entrepreneurs get their marketing knowledge from specialized books and attending of professional conferences though this was minimal among them as contained Table 4.6.

Table 4.6: Sources of marketing knowledge among SMEs in the study area

Major source of Marketing mix knowledge	Frequency	Percentage
From experiences in the course of business	51	76.1
From journals and special books	5	7.5
From participation in professional conferences	8	11.9
The enterprise has a leader with marketing qualification	3	4.5
Total	67	100.0

4.9: Marketing tools employed by SMEs in the Bolgatanga Municipality

The 4Ps marketing as espoused in the literature are considered in this section. Respondents were asked to indicate which of the marketing tools they have been using in their businesses. From Figure 4.6, it can be seen that, promotion is highly patronized among SMEs entrepreneurs in the study area and the least is place. This implies that many SMEs entrepreneurs are motivated to engage in promotional and pricing marketing strategies more than marketing strategies relating to the use of place and product. This finding is consistent with the evidence provided by (Dzisi, 2014) which also found many SMEs in the Eastern Region of Ghana mostly used promotional marketing strategies in the businesses.

Figure 4.2: Marketing mix adoption among SMEs in the Study Area

4.10 Pricing Strategies employed by SMEs in the Bolgatanga Municipality

With respect to pricing activities as a marketing strategy, 84.8% of SMEs entrepreneurs that subscribe pricing as a marketing tool indicated they lower the prices of the goods/services if customers purchase many and different items (see Table 4.7). Cost-based pricing (54.5%) and competitive-based pricing (45.5%) were also

used many SMEs in the study area. The least used pricing policy is valued for money pricing. Perhaps it is least practiced because entrepreneurs are considered profit margins in deciding on which pricing policy to adopt and since value give advantage principally to customers, SMEs will be demotivated to adopt it.

Table 4.7 Pricing Marketing strategies used by SMEs

Pricing Policies among SMEs	Frequency	Percentage
Competitive-based pricing	15	45.5
Cost-based pricing	18	54.5
Valued for money pricing	3	9.1
Lower prices if customers buy many items	28	84.8

4.11 Promotional Strategies employed by SMEs in the Bolgatanga Municipality

In line with promotional marketing strategies, majority of SMEs (83.0%) adhere to Advertisement as their main strategy. This is because, many SMEs entrepreneurs even equate marketing to advertisement. It is there not surprising that among firms that employ promotional mix as their marketing strategy, an overwhelming 83.0% engage in advertisement (see Table 4.8). Again, since many of the SMEs in the study engage in products and services that involve direct contact with their clients or customers, the second most patronized promotional mix marketing strategy is public relations (53.2%). SMEs entrepreneurs need to relate well with the public in order to attract and carve a positive image about their services and to enhance their business operations. Other promotional mixes that are adopted by SMEs in the study are direct marketing and personal selling consistent in the literature.

Table 4.8 Promotional mix marketing strategies employed by SMEs

Promotional mix Marketing strategies among SMEs	Frequency	Percentage
Advertisement	39	83.0
Public Relation	25	53.2
Personal selling	9	19.1
Direct marketing	15	31.9

4.12 Product Strategies employed by SMEs in the Bolgatanga Municipality

Marketing is about identifying, anticipating and satisfying customer needs. SMEs entrepreneurs need to be sure that their products and services continue to meet their customers' needs. One way of guaranteeing customer needs is through product mix as a marketing strategy among SMEs. Many SME adopt product mixes to attract and wow customers and clients to their businesses. The study therefore revealed that quality of products and services (91.7%) and packing (62.5%) are most patronized product marketing mixes among SMEs in the study area. Product support and labelling both stood 37.5% among SMEs (see Table 4.9)

Table 4.9 Product mix marketing strategies among SMEs

Product mix Marketing strategies among SMEs	Frequency	Percentage
Packing	15	62.5
Labelling	9	37.5
High quality products/services	22	91.7
Product support Services	9	37.5

4.13 Place Strategies employed by SMEs in the Bolgatanga Municipality

“Place” is the means of distribution you can select depending on the type of product or service you are marketing. Therefore, the choice of place will even impact on other marketing strategies such as pricing and promotion decisions. The study revealed as shown on Table 4.11 that majority of SMEs (90.5%) entrepreneurs choose to market their product and service by proving their clients or customers appealing business physical atmosphere and decorations. These decorations are meant to draw many customers to their services and products. Some firms also offer after sales delivery (57.1%) in order to lure more clients to their businesses.

Some SMEs entrepreneurs also site their businesses close to where the core of the clients or customer live and thereby making their services and product easily accessible to their clients and customers. Again, only 4 firms in the study consider convenient parking space of vehicles and motor bikes as a marketing tool.

Table 4.10 Place as a marketing mix tool among SMEs

Place as a Marketing mix tool among SMEs	Frequency	Percentage
Close to where many of my customers live/Accessibility	10	47.6
After sales delivery	12	57.1
Business physical atmosphere and decorations are appealing	19	90.5
Convenient parking of vehicles and motor bikes/Conducive and Spacious	4	19.0

Source: Field Survey, 2012

5.0 Conclusion

It was observed that although the vast majority of the SME entrepreneurs adopt some form of marketing, their conception can be described as “primitive and old fashion” and, in general, too limited with respect to the paradigms proposed by academic’s researchers (i.e., the transactional, relationship, and induction marketing). Although none of the three marketing paradigms developed in literature can be considered superior to the others in absolute terms, because their appropriateness varies across contexts (Fruchter and Sigué, 2005), SME entrepreneurs have an incomplete understanding of the marketing concept with respect to each of such paradigms, since they tend to consider it as a synonym of either selling (“A tactics for developing sales and firm size”), or advertising (“A tool for improving consumers’ knowledge of the firm and its products in the marketplace”), thus overemphasizing short-term goals (i.e., sales increases) instead of long-term profitability.

By considering marketing as a mere tactics in support of selling or advertising, rather than as a strategic planning tool, as postulated in the relationship marketing paradigm, or even as a strategic orientation, as postulated in the inductional marketing paradigm, SMEs entrepreneurs in the Bolgatanga Municipality show a “myopia” in marketing concept and adoption (Levitt, 1960). Yet, even though further research on this issue is necessary, there is reason to believe that this sort of “myopia” could be generalized to all SMEs, since recent studies carried out on SMEs located in other countries (Murdoch et al., 2001) have obtained similar results.

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